

Al Serino is an acclaimed American painter, noted for his oil-painted landscapes. By placing himself outside, in the midst of nature, he constantly manages to find new sources of inspiration. Gaining inspiration from a range of sources including serene landscapes, music and the joy of everyday life events, he creates abstract works marked by technical expertise and an emotional backbone. The artist's encounters with landscape and nature influence his art, which is processed and transformed, then reproduced as abstract forms of reality. Primarily driven by interests in existentialism, absurdism and the major contrasts that exist within the human experience, he composes sensitive figurative pieces with interesting balances of monochrome structures next to colorful details. He dances between figurative and abstract styles, weaving pop culture references and bright colours together to achieve a distinctive style.

Al Serino's artwork is showed primarily in the United States, but also many other locations around the world. His work has been featured in many national and international publications. Receiving well deserved accolades throughout his career, Serino's work is often featured in solo and group exhibitions around the nation and abroad and can be found in many private and public collections throughout the world. Attaching great importance to freedom and individuality - both in creativity and life, he composes powerful, high-energy paintings.